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Workpackage 2

Responsible Partner: VFL/EMU

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BIOPIGEE

Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at slaughterhouses

Participating countries

EE (VFL/EMU), IT (IZSLER, ISS), AT (AGES/VMU), UK (APHA), DE (BfR), CZ (VRI), NL (WBVR/UU)

Background

Salmonella and hepatitis E virus (HEV) are zoonotic pathogens that can lead to subclinical infections in pigs, and cause gastrointestinal infections in humans through the food chain. Biosecurity (BS) protocols are important tools for identifying optimal and suboptimal practices in pig slaughterhouses related to the introduction and transmission of infectious pathogens, and can thus help control the occurrence and spread of *Salmonella* and HEV.

Aim and objective

The aim was to identify biosecurity measures that are most effective for limiting *Salmonella* and HEV occurrence and their spread within pig slaughterhouses in order to determine best practice with regards to these pathogens. Furthermore, it was intended to compile a guidance document for slaughterhouses with a collection of evidence-based biosecurity measures for different processes and operations in slaughter line.

To achieve this, the quantitative evidence on effectiveness of measures applied in slaughterhouses to reduce the microbial contamination of pig carcasses was collected from scientific literature.

In regards to hepatitis E virus there are no established biosecurity measures identified to date. Therefore, the aim of the literature search was to collect any published evidence on occurrence and distribution of HEV in slaughter pigs and slaughterhouse environment.

Methods

An extensive literature search was conducted in ISIWoS, Scopus and Google Scholar databases to find relevant sources of scientific information. The keywords used in search terms were: slaughter, biosecurity, abattoir, pig, *Salmonella*, Hepatitis E virus. Publications of original research investigating the effectiveness of measures applied in slaughterhouses were included.

Results

In total, 67 sources of information were selected as potentially useful based on first screening of search results. After the review of the main text of papers, 30 original studies investigating the effectiveness of BS measures in pig slaughterhouses were included and used as a source of scientific evidence of effectiveness. Nine research papers on HEV occurrence and distribution in slaughter pigs and slaughterhouse environment could be identified and were included in a review.

The findings from the literature search on effectiveness of BS measures were summarised according to the steps of slaughter process as follows: General slaughter management; Lairage; Scalding; Singeing; Evisceration; Carcass splitting; Decontamination and Chilling. For all listed slaughter process steps quantitative estimates of effectiveness of important BS measures could be derived from the literature.

Conclusions

There is a substantial amount of quantitative evidence on effectiveness of biosecurity measures in slaughterhouses obtained over recent decades. Based on that the best practices for slaughter hygiene can be established and many of them are reflected in guidelines of the industry organisations like European Livestock and Meat Trades Union (UECBV).

The evidence search on slaughterhouse BS measures has shown that majority of the BS measures for pig slaughter today have been studied from the point of view of faecal *resp.* bacterial contamination with special emphases on limiting the Salmonella contamination on carcasses. No specific measures have been developed to limit the distribution of zoonotic viruses like HEV during slaughtering process yet.

Future work

Further studies on quantification of effectiveness of BS measures to enable evidence-based risk management decisions by decision makers in industry and authorities.

To develop the methods and procedures to limit the spread of HEV in slaughterhouse environment and cross contamination of pig carcasses and quantify their effectiveness.

A publication of the study and its results in a scientific journal is planned.

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